

MƏNBƏŞÜNASLIQ VƏ TARİXŞÜNASLIQ – SOURCE STUDIES AND
HISTORIOGRAPHY

UOT: 94

ERMƏNİSTANIN NAXÇIVAN ƏRAZİSİNƏ DAİR PLANLARI VƏ
AZƏRBAYCAN HÖKUMƏTİNİN ƏKS-TƏDBİRLƏRİ (1918-1920)

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<https://doi.org/10.59849/2523-4765.2024.1.29>

Xülasə: Azərbaycanın ermənilər tərəfindən soyqırımına məruz qalan digər ərazilərində olduğu kimi, Naxçıvan bölgəsində də AXC hökuməti soyqırımı və etnik təmizləmə siyasətinə qarşı tədbirlər görmüş, öz ərazilərini qoruyub saxlamaq və yerli türk əhalisinin hüquqlarını müdafiə etmək istiqamətində fəaliyyət göstərmişdir. Yerli əhalinin bilavasitə iştirakı və Türkiyənin dəstəyi ilə Azərbaycan hökuməti bu istiqamətdə bir sıra hərbi-diplomatik tədbirlər həyata keçirmişdi. Müttəfiq dövlətlərin buradakı bəzi nümayəndələrinin gizli dəstəyinə, Naxçıvan ərazisinə çoxsaylı hücumlarına baxmayaraq Ermənistan bu bölgəni ələ keçirə bilməmişdir. Zəngəzur, İrəvan bölgələrindən fərqli olaraq ermənilər Naxçıvanda türk əhalisinin kütləvi qırılması və təmizlənməsi ilə bağlı planlarını həyata keçirə bilmədilər. Məhz naxçıvanlıların ümumxalq müqaviməti və AXC hökumətinin hərbi-siyasi səyləri nəticəsində Naxçıvan əbədi olaraq Azərbaycanın tərkib hissəsi kimi qaldı.

Məqalənin yazılmasında Azərbaycan arxivlərinin sənədlərindən, İngiltərə və Türkiyənin arxivlərindən götürülmüş və nəşr edilmiş materiallar toplusundan istifadə edilmişdir. Müəllif tədqiqat zamanı mövzuya aid geniş ədəbiyyatdan yararlanmışdır.

AXC hökumətinin ermənilərin müsəlman əhaliyə qarşı həyata keçirdikləri soyqırımı və etnik təmizləməyə, əraziləri iddialarına, o cümlədən Naxçıvana iddialarına qarşı mübarizəsi, bununla bağlı yeni faktların və yanaşmaların ortaya qoyulması davam edən informasiya müharibəsinə dəstəkdir. Bu baxımdan məqalədə araşdırılan məsələlər olduqca aktualdır.

Açar sözlər: Azərbaycan, Türkiyə, Naxçıvan, Ermənistan, soyqırımı, hökumət

ARMENIA'S PLANS ON THE NAKCHIVAN TERRITORY AND THE
COUNTERMEASURES OF THE AZERBAIJAN GOVERNMENT
(1918-1920)

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Abstract: *In the Nakhchivan region, as in other territories of Azerbaijan, the ADR government carried out certain measures to protect and ensure the security of the local Turkic-Muslim population, who were subjected to genocide and ethnic cleansing by Armenian forces, and carried out activities to defend their sovereign rights to this territory. The Azerbaijani government, with the direct participation of the local population and the support of Turkey, has taken political, diplomatic and military steps in this regard. Despite the hidden support of some representatives of the allied states, repeated attacks on the territory of Nakhchivan, Armenia was never able to capture this region. Unlike the regions of Zangezur, İrevan and other territories, in Nakhchivan the Armenians failed to implement their plans for the mass extermination and expulsion of the Turkic population. It was thanks to the popular resistance of the Nakhchivan people and the military-diplomatic efforts of the ADR government that Nakhchivan remained an integral part of Azerbaijan.*

When writing the article, documents from Azerbaijani archives and materials from published collections extracted from the archives of Great Britain and Turkey were used. A wide range of scientific works on the topic under study was subjected to extensive scientific processing.

Studying the history of the struggle of the ADR government against the genocide and ethnic cleansing of the Muslim population by Armenians, their claims on the territory of our country, including Nakhchivan, presenting new facts and new approaches in this regard are an integral part of the ongoing information war. Therefore, the presented topic does not lose its relevance today.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, Turkey, Nakhchivan, Armenia, genocide, government

ПЛАНЫ АРМЕНИИ ПО НАХЧИВАНСКОМУ ТЕРРИТОРИЮ И
КОНТРМЕРЫ ПРАВИТЕЛЬСТВА АЗЕРБАЙДЖАНА (1918-1920 ГГ.)

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Резюме: В Нахчыванском регионе, как и на других территориях Азербайджана, правительство АДР осуществляло определённые меры для защиты и обеспечения безопасности местного тюрко-мусульманского населения, подвергавшегося геноциду и этническим чисткам со стороны армянских формирований, осуществляло активную деятельность по отстаиванию своих суверенных прав на эту территорию. Азербайджанское правительство при непосредственном участии местного населения и поддержке Турции, предприняло политико-дипломатические и военные шаги в этом направлении. Несмотря на скрытую поддержку некоторыми представителями союзных государств, многократные нападения на территорию Нахчывана, Армения так и не смогла захватить этот регион. В отличие от регионов Зангезур, Эривань и других территорий, в Нахчыване армянам не удалось осуществить свои планы массового истребления и изгнания тюркского населения. Именно благодаря всенародному сопротивлению нахчыванцев и военно-дипломатическим усилиям правительства АДР, Нахчыван остался составной частью Азербайджана.

При написании статьи использовались документы азербайджанских архивов, материалы опубликованных сборников, извлечённых из архивов Великобритании и Турции. Был подвергнут широкой научной обработке большой спектр научных трудов по исследуемой теме

Изучение истории борьбы правительства АДР против осуществления армянами геноцида и этнических чисток мусульманского населения, их притязаний на территории нашей страны, включая Нахчыван, представление в связи с этим новых фактов и новых подходов, являются составной частью продолжающейся информационной войны. Поэтому, представленная тема не теряет свою актуальность и сегодня.

Ключевые слова: Азербайджан, Турция, Нахчыван, Армения, геноцид, правительство

ARMENIA'S PLANS ON THE NAKHCHIVAN TERRITORY AND THE COUNTERMEASURES OF THE AZERBAIJAN GOVERNMENT (1918-1920)

Introduction

During the existence of Azerbaijan Democratic Republic (ADR) the government of Azerbaijan attempted to regulate relations with Armenia peacefully, secure diplomatic steps to defend the rights of the Azerbaijani population subjected to genocide by the Republic of Ararat (Armenia), provide financial and spiritual assistance to refugees, and protect their historical lands from occupation. The territorial claims pretended by Armenia against the Nakhchivan region were not

satisfied in a peaceful way, and as a result, Armenian political circles implemented the policy of genocide and ethnic cleansing against Azerbaijanis, accompanied by military intervention against the historical territories of Azerbaijan. Besides with other territories claimed by Armenians (Zangazur, Karabakh, part of Gazakh province), the ADR government conducted a diplomatic struggle to resolve disputed issues in the Nakhchivan region, asked foreign countries for help in preventing genocide, and demanded decisive measures.

After the decree on the genocide of Azerbaijanis¹ signed by the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan on March 26, 1998, an order was issued to mark March 31 as genocide day every year. This is a manifestation of the fact that the state always focuses on genocide issues. The struggle of the ADR government against genocide and ethnic cleansing, the study of their results, the investigation of the reasons why the Armenians in Nakhchivan could not entirely implement the genocide, and the introduction of new facts support the proceeding information war. The issues investigated in the article are very relevant in terms of the fight against the provocations and territorial claims of Armenia that continue today.

Researches and recently discovered documents² demonstrate that Turkey began to gradually withdraw its army until the Armistice of Mudros due to the September 23 German-Turkish agreement and Turkey's personal political interests. After the Peace of Mudros, the remaining Turkish troops departed from the Caucasus region.

Military, political and social situation in Nakhchivan

The Armenian government nominated territorial claims to implement its expansionist policy, and in order to justify these claims legally, it reduced the number of the local Muslim population by committing a genocide and ethnic cleansing policy. When the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic was established, its territory was 113.9 thousand square kilometers. The Republic of Armenia raised territorial claims to 16.6 thousand square kilometers of this territory.³ One of these alleged areas was Nakhchivan, the historical land of Azerbaijan. The majority of the population in Nakhchivan territory consisted of Azerbaijanis. This was also confirmed by the British Foreign Office. The information sent to the military office stated that the main population of Nakhchivan, whose northern and southern borders have not yet been completely determined, consists of Tatars (Azerbaijani – J.N.) and that this territory has never been seriously invaded by the Republic of Armenia.⁴

¹ Azərbaycanlıların soyqırımı haqqında Azərbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin fərmanı, **Azərbaycan Respublikası prezidentinin rəsmi internet saytı**. Bakı, 26 mart, 1998.

² Azərbaycan Xalq Cümhuriyyəti. **Böyük Britaniyanın arxiv sənədləri**. Bakı, Çəşioğlu, 2008, s.96-97; s.167.

³ İsmayıl Hacıyev. **Ermənilərin Azərbaycana qarşı ərazi iddiaları və qanlı cinayətləri**, Naxçıvan, Əcəmi. 2012, s.48.

⁴ **Документы Британского национального архива по истории Южного Кавказа 1918-1920 годов**. Баку, Турхан ИПО, т.1, ч.1, 2020, с.188.

Some Armenian authors argue that the majority of the population of Nakhchivan consisted of Armenians, and that the number of the Armenian population decreased as a result of the Baku operation by the Turkish army in 1918.⁵ However, the above source also confirms that the majority of the population in Nakhchivan, which the Armenians noted as a disputed territory, was Muslim.

The fact that Armenians were less than Azerbaijanis is also given in their own press and official documents. According to the Armenian press, in November 1919, 70.000 Armenians lived in Sharur and Nakhchivan.⁶

Territorial claims, the plan to change the population composition impelled the Armenian government to military aggression. Armenia considered Nakhchivan the territory of Armenians and intervened there militarily in May-June 1918. However, the Armenians were defeated in the territories of Khanliq and Ulya Norashen and retreated to Dereleyez.⁷

Then, in July 1918, Armenian armed groups led by Andranik captured Nakhchivan and declared that weapons would be confiscated from the population and those who opposed the government would be punished. To implement all this, Andranik inquired Stepan Shaumyan for help and received a positive response.⁸ Thus, the expansive military aggression of Armenia to Nakhchivan began. Although Andranik declared that was a subject of the Russian Bolsheviks, he actually defended the interests of the Armenian state. On August 4, 1918, the chairman of the Baku Armenian Council noted that there were 25 thousand Armenian troops in Iravan under the leadership of Nazarbeyov, and the national hero Andranik was in Nakhchivan. Armenians in the occupied territories (by the Turks – J.N.) support the Baku Council.⁹ Apparently, the Baku Armenian Council, which considers itself a branch of the Armenian Council in Iravan, called Andranik a national hero.

Since Nakhchivan was transferred to the control of Turkey according to the Batumi Treaty of June 4, 1918, the military aggression of Armenia to this region was assessed as a violation of the terms of the treaty. Therefore, the Ottoman troops entered the territory of Nakhchivan and attempted to organize the defense of the region and protect the Muslim population. With the support of Turkey, the local Muslims were defeated from the Armenians on July 20. Andranik's group first moved to Gorus and then to Sisian.¹⁰

⁵ Армен Хачикян. **История Армении (краткий очерк)**. Эреван, Эдит Принт, 2009, с.13.

⁶ **Документы Британского национального архива по истории Южного Кавказа 1918-1920 годов**. Баку, Турхан ИПО, т.1, ч.2, 2020, с.160.

⁷ Kamran İsmayılov. **Azərbaycanın Naxçıvan bölgəsi regional hərbi-siyasi proseslərdə (1917-1920)**. Bakı, Turxan NPB, 2019, s.31-32.

⁸ İbrahim Atnur, **Osmanlı idarəçiliyindən Sovet idarəçiliyinə qədər Naxçıvan (1918-1921)**. Naxçıvan, Əcəmi, 2013, s.57-58.

⁹ Azərbaycan Xalq Cümhuriyyəti. **Böyük Britaniyanın arxiv sənədləri**. Bakı, Çarşıoğlu, 2008, s.98-103.

¹⁰ İbrahim Atnur. **Indicated book**, p.60.

On September 23, 1918, a secret protocol on the withdrawal of Turkish troops from Azerbaijan was signed between Talat Pasha and Germany in Berlin. By signing this protocol, which completely changed the Turkish policy in Azerbaijan, Talat Pasha correctly assessed the military situation. The danger of the invasion of Bulgaria was approaching, and 4 divisions were extradited to Constantinople by Turkey. A part of the Turkish army that liberated Baku remained in Azerbaijan in order to prevent the massacres that the Armenians might commit.¹¹

On October 23, 1918, the Turkish High Command issued a definitive order to evacuate troops from Iran and the Caucasus beyond the borders (Kars, Ardahan and Batum) defined by the terms of the Brest-Litovsk Peace, and the Eastern Army Group was officially disbanded. However, Turkey was worried that Armenia, especially Andranik's gangs, would resume their hostile policy.¹²

It was believed in the scientific literature that the Turkish army left Azerbaijan and the Caucasus after the terms of the Mudros Treaty. Researches and recently discovered documents above show that Turkey started to gradually withdraw its army until the Mudros Treaty due to the September 23 German-Turkish agreement and Turkey's own political interests. After the Peace of Mudros, the remaining Turkish troops left the Caucasus region. However, Turkey found another way to stay in the Caucasus by nominating Turkish officers to the leadership of the Azerbaijani army. The last Turkish army left Azerbaijan on December 22, 1918.¹³

Having received the news about the leaving of the Turks the South Caucasus, the Armenians again continued the genocide and ethnic cleansing in Nakhchivan and other Azerbaijani territories. In addition to important issues such as the promotion of the country in the international arena, in foreign policy the ADR government was forced to act in the direction of preventing Armenia's military intervention and genocide attempt in Nakhchivan. This situation impeded to ensure the security and prosperity of the South Caucasus region, as well as the peaceful living of the countries and residents of the region.

In the article the representatives of Nakhchivan-Zangibasar published in "Communist" newspaper on October 15, 1920 about the "situation in Nakhchivan-Zangibasar region" noted that "the properties of the residents of Zangibasar, Vedibasar, Sharur, Shahtakhti, Dereleyez were plundered, 500.000 residents became poor, 45.000 refugees perished from hunger and disease, about 70.000 displaced people were settled in Iran".¹⁴

Military and diplomatic actions

¹¹ Azərbaycan Xalq Cümhuriyyəti. **Böyük Britaniyanın arxiv sənədləri**. Bakı, Çarşıoğlu, 2008, s.96.

¹² **Ibid**, p.96-97.

¹³ **Ibid**, p.167.

¹⁴ Илгар Нифталиев. **Геноцид азербайджанцев в Иреванской губернии (1918-1920)**. Баку, Турхан, 2014, p.84.

The military and diplomatic measures implemented by the ADR government in the fight against the genocide, ethnic cleansing, military aggression, and territorial claims of the Republic of Armenia were of significant importance.

Established on November 30, 1918 by the local Turkish population in order to protect themselves from the Armenians, which covers a part of Echmiadzin district, Sardarabad, Ulukhanli, Gamarli, Vedi, Sharur, Nakhchivan, Ordubad, Mehri and Surmeli regions, the capital is the city of Nakhchivan, the area is about 16 thousand square kilometers, the population of which is close to 1 million people, the Araz-Turkish Republic announced in the first government declaration on January 4, 1919 that Nakhchivan has always been considered a part of Azerbaijan and expects support from Azerbaijan against the military aggression of Armenia.¹⁵

In January 1919, the Armenian leadership prepared to attack Nakhchivan again. By the decision of the Armenian government on January 14, 1919, Shelkovnikyan was appointed the governor-general of Nakhchivan. The government of Azerbaijan and the government of Araz-Turkish Republic took defensive measures, the population was armed.¹⁶

On January 21, 1919, an agreement was signed between Azerbaijanis and Armenians in Nakhchivan with the participation of a British officer, however a few days later, the battle between them started again in Kemerli, 19 versts from Iravan. In Nakhchivan, 100 British soldiers could maintain order.¹⁷

By the decision of the Azerbaijan government on February 28, 1919, the General Governorate of South-Western Azerbaijan was established in order to ensure the protection of the Nakhchivan region. Bahram Khan Nakhchivanski was appointed the governor-general, Kerim Khan Iravanski and Haji Mehdi Bagirov was appointed as deputies. In March, Hashimbeyov was appointed the governor-general of the General Governorate of South-Western Azerbaijan.¹⁸

In March 1919, Armenian armed forces again attacked Nakhchivan in 3 directions – Beyukduz, Tugh and Ordubad. 10.000-men Armenian army attacked Ordubad and captured Kolun, Tund, Dilavar Khan, Khanabadi, Torec, Dehsar, etc. they completely plundered Muslim villages and massacred their population. The villages of Kodareh, Attayat, Dirnes, Otusel, Aylis, Daraghort, Hachadagh (Nochedogh) were again destroyed by Armenians and their population was massacred.¹⁹

¹⁵ İsmayıl Hacıyev. **Indicated book**, p.56-57; Elman Cəfərli. **Naxçıvanda erməni-Azərbaycan münaqişəsi**. Bakı, Nurlan, 2009, s.198-199.

¹⁶ Kamran İsmayılov. **Indicated book**, p.47.

¹⁷ Документы **Британского национального архива по истории Южного Кавказа 1918-1920 годов**. Баку, Турхан ИПО, т.1, ч.1, 2020, с.135.

¹⁸ Kamran İsmayılov. **Indicated book**, p.59.

¹⁹ Документы **Британского национального архива по истории Южного Кавказа 1918-1920 годов**. Баку, Турхан ИПО, т.1, ч.1, 2020, p.151.

The ADR government responded to Armenia's aggressive action with a note of protest. On March 24, 1919, the diplomatic representative of the Azerbaijan Republic in Armenia, M.Tekinsky, sent a telegram to the Minister of Foreign Affairs of Armenia demanding an immediate cessation of aggression, otherwise relations would be disrupted.²⁰

However, the authorities of Ararat (Armenia) disregarded these demands and proceeded their expansionist and genocide policy. On April 12, 1919, M.Kh.Tekin-sky objected to the presence of Armenian troops in the territory of Azerbaijan in his letter sent to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Armenia.²¹

The military aggression of the Armenian government to Nakhchivan was also in the focus of the British. They believed the arguments of the Armenians and agreed the annexation of Nakhchivan to Armenia. On April 6 (1919), the Armenian leadership proposed that the British troops in the region could be replaced by Armenian troops. The Azerbaijani government immediately protested this and emphasized that the majority of the population of Nakhchivan consists of Azerbaijanis. The British headquarters confirmed that this information is true.²²

On May 3, 1919, a document on the annexation of Nakhchivan to Armenia was signed between the British representative General K.M.Davie and D.Kanayan. On May 13, representatives of the Armenian government led by G.Varshamian arrived in Nakhchivan.²³

In his ciphered telegram of May 10, 1919 addressed to the Chairman of the Council of Ministers N.Usubbeyov, M.T.Tekinsky stated that "according to speculation, the British are handing the Sharur-Nakhchivan region to Armenia on the condition that Armenia recognizes Karabakh as an Azerbaijani territory. Sharur-Nakhchivan, whose population is entirely Muslim, may not be handed to Armenia. Since the population of Sharur-Nakhchivan will be in a terrible situation like the Muslims inhabiting in other parts of Armenia. It is necessary to thoroughly explain this to the allied command in Tiflis and to be in constant contact with it, otherwise our diplomacy will fail".²⁴

²⁰ **Azərbaycan xalqına qarşı 1918-ci il Mart soyqırımı.** Sənədlər toplusu. İrəvan Quberniyasında soyqırımı (1918-1920-ci illər): Bakı, Çarşioğlu, c.2 (2-ci kitab), 2011, s.64-65.

²¹ **Министру Иностранных Дел Республики Армении. Дипломатический Представитель Азербайджанской Республики при Правительств Республики Армени М.Х.Текинский.** (Эривань: 12 апреля 1919), **Azərbaycan Respublikası Dövlət Arxivi (ARDA).** Fond №897, siy.№2, iş №36, v.83.

²² **Документы Британского национального архива по истории Южного Кавказа 1918-1920 годов.** Баку, Турхан ИПО, т.1, ч.1, 2020, с.409.

²³ **Armenia in documents of the U.S. Department of State 1917-1920.** Yerevan, Institute of History NAS of Armenia, 2017, p.350; Gayane Makhmourian, Collection of Papers Relating to the Armenian District of Nakhijevan (1918-1920) from the U.S. Department of State and the National Archives of Armenia, **Fundamental Armenology**, number 2(4), 2016, p.350.

²⁴ **Шифрованная телеграмма из Эривани. Баку. Министру-Председателю.** Копия Товарищу Министра-Иностранных дель. Дипломатический Представитель Текин-ский. (Эривань: 10 мая 1919). **ARDA.** Fond №970, siy.№1, iş №62, v.42.

On June 21, 1919, until the arrival of the US troops, the regions of Nakhchivan, Sharur, Vedibasar, Shahtakhti and Julfa were occupied by Armenian troops and Armenian rule was established in these areas. Azerbaijan's diplomatic representative in Armenia, Muhammad Khan Tekinski, informed about this in a ciphered telegram to the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of ADR (Mammed Yusif Jafarov). He added that "Ordubad is not still in the hands of Armenians; however this region can be occupied at any moment."²⁵

As a result of the military aggression of Armenia, the Azerbaijanis, who were persecuted and massacred, commenced to leave their places. In this case, the government of Azerbaijan stopped the transportation of fuel - oil and kerosene allocated for the Armenian railway due to the military aggression that occurred in Nakhchivan. This product is of strategic importance for the Armenian army and was extensively used for military purposes. In July 1919, the diplomatic representative of Azerbaijan in Iravan, M.Kh.Tekinski sent a telegram to the Prime Minister and the Minister of Foreign Affairs of ADR, requesting that not a pound of fuel oil or kerosene should be allowed to be sent to Armenians until the Muslim villagers return to their homes and their leased lands are returned to them.²⁶

In addition, the Azerbaijani government commenced to determine military measures against aggression. The military situation in Nakhchivan was learned from Tekinski, the representative in Iravan. It became clear that the Sharur-Nakhchivan region can organize 6.000 regular troops armed with cavalry, mechanical weapons and machine guns. The British also admitted that they fought well. Besides, Tekinski reported that the Armenians supplied flour that could provide the army for 8 months, the Armenians purchased 200 miles (military supplies, fuel) from the British for 1.5 million rubles, and considered Denikin (one of the leaders of the volunteer troops who fought for power in Russia against the Bolsheviks) is the man saving the Armenia after the British left the region.²⁷

Assessing the situation, the Azerbaijan government sent troops to Nakhchivan and besieged the area. On July 27, 10.000 – men Azerbaijani army under the leadership of Turkish officer Khalil Bey established a position in Sharur-Dereleyez district and suggested to Armenia ending hostilities and accepting Sharur-Dereleyez and Nakhchivan as belonging to Azerbaijan. Having received the news that the Azerbaijani army lacked weapons and ammunition, the Armenians did not accept the offer and continued the attack, nevertheless were defeated and retreated to Kemerli.²⁸

²⁵ **Azərbaycan xalqına qarşı 1918-ci il Mart soyqırımı.** Sənədlər toplusu. İrəvan Quberniyasında soyqırımı (1918-1920-ci illər): Bakı, Çarşıoğlu, c.2 (2-ci kitab). 2011, s.114.

²⁶ **Azərbaycan Xalq Cümhuriyyəti. Böyük Britaniyanın arxiv sənədləri.** Bakı, Çarşıoğlu, 2008, s.200.

²⁷ **Документы Британского национального архива по истории Южного Кавказа 1918-1920 годов.** Баку, Турхан ИПО, т.1, ч.1, 2020, с.381-382.

²⁸ **Indicated book**, p.420.

The government of Azerbaijan was proceeding to fight against the aggression of Armenia, establishing international relations, discussing with the commanders of the Allied troops in the Caucasus and being able to prove that Armenia's territorial claims are baseless. Later, the negative attitude of the British and American representatives towards Azerbaijan changed to a positive as a result of the countermeasures of the ADR government. As a result of the support of Allied missions, British and American, the Armenian army could achieve some military successes. The departure of the British bothered the Armenian government. Armenian official Korganov stated that "the army limited in terms of weapons and ammunition, they were not scared anything during the British troops stayed in Armenia, and they would face significant danger if a complete evacuation occurred"²⁹.

The purpose of the Armenians, who sent such information to the world, was to defame Azerbaijan as a country that committed genocide in front of the British command and the world community. However, studies and documents demonstrate that Armenia was implementing an expansion ethnic cleansing policy by declaring territorial claims against Azerbaijan and subjecting the Muslim population of those areas to genocide. The fact that there are no sources about the massacre of Armenians after the British left Azerbaijan proves the above-said. The response to such provocative data of the Armenians was to calm the Armenians. British intelligence reported on August 15: "We are effortful in attempting to restore order and open communication to ensure the normal activity and possible influence of British military representative in Iravan, Colonel Plowden, who hopes to move to Nakhchivan today. However, we cannot send troops"³⁰.

Apparently, the Armenian side needed the support of the British to wage war against Azerbaijan and the Turkish army. Meanwhile, Azerbaijani diplomacy expanded its political activities, and the British, who had previously believed in the propaganda of Armenian official circles and expressed a positive attitude to Armenia's demands, had already commenced to consider Azerbaijan's position. The situation in Nakhchivan was remaining tense and the war was proceeding between Armenians and Azerbaijanis. On July 20, the remaining places, except the north of the city, transferred under the control of the Azerbaijanis, who cut the telegraph lines so that the enemies could not communicate. The British mission was in the south of the city, and the American hospitals and shelters were in the north. In such a situation, Plowden, the British military representative in Iravan, ordered the immediate withdrawal of the British mission from Nakhchivan. Captain Schwind and Lieutenant Johnson left town. Later in the evening, Captain Schwind was dispatched to Nakhchivan to discuss the cessation of hostilities between the Armenian civil authority and his staff and the Azerbaijani Kalbali Khan and his staff. Both sides signed an agreement to cease fighting for 3 days to allow Colonel Plowden to investigate the indicated problem. However, discussions about identification of the culprits were not permitted, the battle proceeded. At the

²⁹ Indicated book, p.463.

³⁰ Indicated book, p.447.

end of July 1919, with the support of the Ottoman army, Nakhchivan was completely recaptured from the Armenians.³¹

On August 21, 1919, the representatives of Nakhchivan in Tbilisi adopted a decision to keep Nakhchivan region within the ADR.³²

The settlement of border issues with Armenia in Zangezur, Nakhchivan and Sharur was delayed due to Armenia's territorial claims. The proposal of the Allies High Commissioner of the South Caucasus, Colonel Haskel, to create a neutral zone in the districts of Sharur-Darelayaz and Nakhchivan³³ was not accepted as a result of the strong opposition³⁴ and purposeful policy of the Azerbaijani government.³⁵

The plan of the Armenians to change the numerical composition of the population in Nakhchivan, the genocidal policy purposed at artificially increasing the number of Armenians and, as a result, the capture of the region within the framework of international law principles, did not implement. Azerbaijani representatives were able to convince the world powers in Paris that the territories considered disputed by Armenians, including Nakhchivan, are not historical Armenian lands. As a result, the peace conference refused to give those territories to Armenia and kept the border issue open while recognizing the states.³⁶ On January 11, 1920, the Supreme Council of the Paris Peace Conference adopted a decision on the de facto recognition of Azerbaijan and Georgia as independent states.³⁷

Thus, the Armenian government lost both in diplomacy and on the battlefield as a result of the measures implemented by the ADR government in the Nakhchivan region.

Other implemented measures

The local population, intellectuals and public organizations supported the measures of the ADR government to prevent genocide and ethnic cleansing in Nakhchivan, conditions were created for refugees to be accommodated, returned to their places and provided with food and other necessary supplies.

³¹ Документы Британского национального архива по истории Южного Кавказа 1918-1920 годов. Баку, Турхан ИПО, т. 1, ч. 2, 2020, р.191.

³² Elman Cəfərli. **Indicated book**, p.212-213; Kamran İsmayılov. **Indicated book**, p.78-86.

³³ **От полковника Виляма Н.Гаскеля Союзаго Верховнаго Комиссара.** Председателю Совета Министров Азербайджана (Тифлис: 1 сентября 1919). **ARDA.** Fond №970, siy.№1, iş №93, v.3-4.

³⁴ **Тифлис. Верхнему Комиссару Закавказья подполковнику Гаскелю.** От Минстр Иностраннных дел Азербайджанской Республики Джафаров. (Баку: 29 сентября 1919). **Azərbaycan Respublikası Prezidentinin İşlər İdarəsinin İctimai-Siyasi Sənədlər Arxivi (ARPIİİSSA).** Fond №277, siyahı №2, iş №96, vərəq 46.

³⁵ Azərbaycan Xalq Cümhuriyyəti. **Böyük Britaniyanın arxiv sənədləri.** Bakı, Çarşıoğlu, 2008, s.263-264; s.388.

³⁶ **Indicated book**, p.407.

³⁷ **Azərbaycan Paris sülh konfransında** (1919-1920). Bakı, Ozan, 2008, s.5-8.

In the ADR Parliament (4th session in 1918, 7th, 9th, 21st, 29th, 35th, 46th, 55th, 56th, 57th 109th sessions in 1919, 132nd, 142nd sessions in 1920) the policy of genocide and ethnic cleansing enforced by the Armenian armed forces in Nakhchivan was discussed and measures were implemented.³⁸

The government of Azerbaijan was also implementing measures to improve the situation of refugees. ADR MFA periodically informed representatives of foreign countries in the Caucasus about the situation of refugees and requested them to help. MFA F. Khoyski addressed General Thomson and informed that the authorities decided to send their representatives – T.Makinski, R.Ismayilov and doctor Ganizade – to Nakhchivan, Sharur, Surmeli, Vedibasari and Millistan in order to determine the exact situation of the refugees. Bagir Rzayev, Maharram Aliyev, Ali Ashraf Kazimov, Huseyn Javid, Asad Manafov, Bahran Khan and Aziz Khan Nakhchivansky, representatives of the Muslim population who came to Baku to inform the authorities about the situation of Muslim refugees and appeal for help, are returning together with the representatives of the authorities. “I request you to 1) order the representative to return to the specified regions without hindrance; 2) if possible, provide the representative escorts from British soldiers along the way; 3) send a letter to the British authorities about assisting the specified regions”.³⁹

The representative of the government in Iravan, Ali Khan Makinsky, opened the way to Nakhchivan to support the refugees in the region through the American mission. On October 1, 1919, he informed the Ministry of Foreign Affairs that contact was established with Nakhchivan through the American mission, and food, money, medical supplies and other parcels could be sent to the refugees from our side.⁴⁰

In 1918-1920, the local population, who suffered from the policy of genocide and ethnic cleansing directed against the people of Azerbaijan by the Republic of Ararat, attempted to avoid the depressed situation they were in at the expense of their own resources, and established a number of public organizations to solve the problems. These public organizations effected to prevent genocides by attempting to normalize relations between the two neighboring countries (ADR and Ararat), and accomplished measures to improve the circumstance of Azerbaijani refugees who were forced to leave their homeland as a result of the ethnic cleansing policy of the Republic of Ararat. Public organizations also realized the work of notifying the ADR government about the political and military situation on the front. In

³⁸ **Azərbaycan Xalq Cümhuriyyəti** (1918-1920). Parlament (Stenoqrafik hesabatlar), c.1. Bakı, Azərbaycan nəşriyyatı, 1998, s.75; s.112; s.142; s.264; s.330; s.396; s.498; s.570; s.613; s.650; **Azərbaycan Xalq Cümhuriyyəti** (1918-1920). Parlament (Stenoqrafik hesabatlar), c.2. Bakı, Azərbaycan nəşriyyatı, 1998, s.479; s.631; s.721.

³⁹ **Командующему Союзными Силами в Тифлис Генералу Томсону**. Министр Председатель Хойский. (Баку: 3 апреля 1919). **ARPIIISSA**. Fond №277, siy.№2, iş №57, v.5.

⁴⁰ Министру Иностранных Дель. Дипломатический Представитель при Правительстве Армении (Эривань: 1 октября 1919). **ARPIIISSA**. Fond №277, siy.№1, iş №58, v.73.

September 1918, a public organization called the Union and Solidarity League of the Caucasian Peoples, founded in Baku by a number of Armenian and Muslim public figures, propagandized in order to create solidarity and friendship between Turks and Armenians.⁴¹

All charitable societies attempted to improve the circumstance of the population as much as possible before the Soviet occupation. After the Soviet occupation, they were abolished.

The people of Nakhchivan efforted to prevent the massacre of the population on their personal initiative by writing letters to various official circles, and notified of the ethnic cleansing policy implemented by the Armenians. During the Batum negotiations, Ganja and Iravan Muslim National Councils, Pan-Caucasus Muslim Central Committee sent a letter of appeal to Chief Minister Talat Pasha about the massacre of Muslims in Nakhchivan, Karabakh, and Iravan regions by Armenians. The letter stated that the ammunition left by the Russians was seized by the Armenian bands, Muslims could not obtain weapons from the Caucasian government to defend themselves, and therefore Muslims were killed by Armenians, expelled from their places and subjected to ethnic cleansing.⁴²

The local Turkish population also dispatched protest letters to the Armenian government. In a letter dated May 15, 1919, the Muslim population of Nakhchivan stated to the Prime Minister of Armenia that “we observed the violence against the Muslim nation with the transfer of Nakhchivan-Sharur-Ordubad regions to the administration of the Republic of Armenia and expressed our rightful protest to General Thomson. We inform you as a representative of the Republic of Armenia that you should not agree with this violence and you cannot enter our regions until this question is resolved at the conference”.⁴³

Individual influential persons from Nakhchivan also accomplished various measures and provided financial assistance to protect the local Turkish population from massacres. An example of them is Kalbali Khan in Nakhchivan and Fatulla Bey Huseynov in Sharur.⁴⁴

As a result of the protection of Nakhchivan by the ADR government, public organizations and the local population, measures implemented to prevent the genocide and ethnic cleansing committed by Armenians, Nakhchivan was not captured by the Armenian ruling circles.

In 1920, after the Sovietization of Armenia, the genocide in Nakhchivan suspended and Nakhchivan was remained within the Azerbaijan SSR. According to

⁴¹ Nəşib Nəşibzadə. **Azərbaycanın xarici siyasəti** (1918-1920). Bakı, Ay-Ulduz, 1996, s.83.

⁴² **Azərbaycan Cumhuriyeti 1918-1920** (Osmanlı Arşiv Belgeleri). İstanbul, Bilnet Matbaacılık ve Yayıncılık. A.Ş., 2018, s.143-144.

⁴³ Премьер Министру Республики Армении. От Мусульман Нахчевана. (Нахчевань: 15 мая 1919), **ARPIISSA**. Fond №277, siy.№2, iş №57, v.14.

⁴⁴ Nail Əliyev. **1917-1920-ci illərdə Azərbaycanda türk-müsəlman soyqırımları ilk mənbələrdə**. Bakı, Nurlan, 2007, s.61.

Elman Jafarli's research, 73,727 Azerbaijanis were killed by Armenians in the Nakhchivan region in 1918-1921, the population decreased by 38 percent, and in 1921, Armenians constituted only 12 percent of the population of Nakhchivan.⁴⁵

Conclusion

The Azerbaijan Democratic Republic has always struggled to prevent the genocide and ethnic cleansing, territorial claims committed by Armenians against Azerbaijanis in the form of appeals and notes. The local people accomplished measures against the expansion of massacres at the expense of their own resources and with the support of local charities. Proving that the territories claimed by the Armenian government, including Nakhchivan, are the ancient land of Azerbaijan was also part of the diplomatic struggle. The government of the ADR succeeded in this mission, and neither the representatives of the great powers in the Caucasus nor the Paris Peace Conference recognized the territories claimed by the Armenians, including Nakhchivan, as belonging to the Armenians. Influential countries such as the United Kingdom and the United States supported the ADR government. The struggle of the Azerbaijani government resulted in a victory over Armenia, and the plan of genocide and ethnic cleansing of Armenians in the Nakhchivan region did not accomplish.

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⁴⁵ Elman Cəfərli. **Indicated book**, p.223-225.

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